

THE ROLE OF MEDIA IN TURKEY'S DEMOCRATIZATION PROCESS**Maral Najafli***Dr., Faculty of Communication, Department of Journalism
Independent Researcher*ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-1254-4969>**Abstract**

While democracy is built upon fundamental principles such as freedom of expression, transparency, and accountability, the media stands out as a key actor contributing to the healthy functioning of these principles. This study examines the historical development of the media in Turkey during its democratization process, its influence on political dynamics, and the challenges encountered in this context. The aim of the study is to evaluate how Turkish media has impacted democratization processes, under what conditions it has supported or hindered this process, and to reveal the fundamental dynamics in the media-democracy relationship.

The methodology employed includes literature review and document analysis. In this context, academic studies, historical documents, legal regulations, and period-specific publications of media outlets related to the media-democracy relationship in Turkey have been analyzed.

The study covers various periods, including Turkey's transition from a single-party regime to a multi-party system, periods of military interventions, the privatization of the media sector, and the political influences on media in the digital era. The findings shed light on both the supportive and limiting roles of the media in the democratization process. Furthermore, it provides a critical perspective on the current issues faced by the media in Turkey concerning freedom, independence, and pluralism.

Keywords: Turkey, Media, Democratization Process, Freedom of Expression**The Effects of Media on the Democratization Process**

Media refers to the fundamental components that enable the interaction of mass communication tools with society. Historically, media has evolved from being a communication tool primarily of interest to specialists to becoming a central mechanism shaping social phenomena such as family, gender identities, urban environments, and nations (Maigret, 2004: 27). The relationship between media and democracy becomes evident through the media's capacity to connect individuals, support or weaken power structures, and shape cultures (Maigret, 2004: 42).

Thompson (2008: 45) defines media in two aspects: technical media and communication media. Technical media refers to the physical tools through which information and symbolic content are fixed and disseminated, while communication media encompasses specific institutions and products such as books, newspapers, television, and radio programs. These definitions emphasize the impact of media on social relations and the transmission of political agendas.

The role of media in building a democratic culture is critical. When the media becomes dependent on political parties, it deepens the language of conflict in the political culture of society and transforms into a propaganda tool. The complex relationship between media and politics is built on mutual interests and needs; media relies on politics as a source of news, while politicians require media to disseminate their messages (Geçer, 2018: 481). However, media's independence from political pressures is essential for contributing to democratic development and societal transformation.

Identifying reform opportunities and removing obstacles to strengthen the media sector is a strategic necessity. This process is achievable with a conscious, balanced, and objective press. The way media com-

municates with the masses is also significant; for example, radio is an effective tool in rural areas and in countries with low literacy rates, while television and print media primarily reach urban and educated audiences (Center for Democracy and Governance, 1999: 7).

The elements supporting the development of the media sector include consumers, journalists, content provider companies, educational institutions, independent regulatory authorities, media watchdogs, professional organizations, and new technology providers. According to Plattner (2012: 67), political parties, media, and civil society—three main channels shaping individuals' thoughts—are not part of official government structures but are essential mechanisms that determine the functioning and quality of democratic states. Therefore, the presence and quality of press freedom are directly related to democracy.

Media exhibits varying reflections on whether it serves democracy and freedom of expression. If the media contributes to the dissemination of democratic ideals, amplifies the voices of conflicting parties, provides society with high-quality and up-to-date information, represents social benefits, and facilitates public debates, it serves democratic goals and press freedom (Ullah, 2009: 345). In this context, the roles and functions that media should undertake are closely linked to the fundamental indicators of normative media theories. According to Trappel, normative media and journalism theories can be classified into the triad of freedom/information, oversight/observation, and equality/forum (Trappel and Tomaz, 2021: 7). Press freedom can only be fully realized if the media possesses the qualities required to fulfill these functions, as this indicates the presence of an environment where democratization can largely be achieved.

In democratic societies, an environment where mandatory illusions cannot be imposed and debates are

not prohibited is essential. However, the danger of independent thought turning into a political activity always exists. At this point, the concept of "limits of what can be expressed" becomes significant, as freedom of the press inherently includes freedom of expression. To prevent potential dangers, the boundaries of what can be expressed must be clearly defined (Chomsky, 2012: 71-72). These boundaries should not serve any interest group, must encompass all aspects of public opinion, and encourage public participation.

The right of citizens to learn and be informed about events in state affairs is a fundamental feature of democratic systems. Hence, democratic political systems are referred to as "regimes of transparency." In these regimes, individuals have the natural right to access information, interpret what they learn, investigate, and critique in all matters related to daily life. The media is the most effective tool for ensuring these rights. However, the right to learn and be informed is not limited to the mere transmission of events; it also requires the presentation of opinions, interpretations, and criticisms regarding these events. These elements are essential for individuals to fully exercise their right to learn, and in this regard, press freedom represents a highly interactive process (Akarca, 1989: 266). Such a process is only possible in a democratic environment.

Media and communication studies recognize that the news media assumes specific roles in democracy (Trappel and Tomaz, 2021: 13). These roles determine the topics and extent to which the media functions. To strengthen democracy, the media plays a critical role with its broad influence. To fulfill this role, the media must possess six features: access, information, discussion, negotiation, preference, and action (Cenkins and Thorburn, 2003, as cited in Ceyhan, 2020: 110). Through these features, the media can undertake the tasks of monitoring and critiquing government policies and actions, contribute to public opinion formation through social awareness, and become a crucial element of democracy with its balance and oversight role.

One of the fundamental characteristics of modern democratic societies is the principle of transparency and openness. This principle requires all transactions to be carried out in the public eye and ensures public participation in decision-making processes. The media, as the observing eye, hearing ear, and speaking voice of society, enables individuals to respond appropriately by presenting events accurately, comprehensively, and impartially (Işık, 2005: 116). Furthermore, the media has roles in establishing and activating democratic codes, maintaining the system, and exposing undemocratic situations (Ceyhan, 2020: 110). Through these roles, it becomes possible to expose undemocratic governance elements developed against societal changes.

For democracy to be understood in a pluralistic sense, a polyphonic or multi-voiced media is necessary (Dukul, 2022: 77). Pluralistic media plays an important role in creating awareness against the "othering" of individuals or preventing the exclusion of socially and politically disadvantaged groups (Ceyhan, 2020: 112). In this context, the media's democratic role as the voice and protector of public opinion and its ability to monitor power come to the fore.

According to Müller's approach, the media's contribution to democracy can be analyzed through two main frameworks: vertical communication and horizontal relationships. Vertical communication involves the government, politics, and citizens, emphasizing functions such as providing information, press freedom, accountability, transparency, and equal and easy access. Horizontal relationships involve intermediary actors and political representatives, focusing on promoting responsiveness within mechanisms of freedom of expression and press freedom (Müller, 2012, as cited in Ceyhan, 2020: 112). Access to the media and public discussions is a prerequisite for individuals to exercise their rights. At this point, new media opportunities come into play; as platforms where the public can also produce content and reach large audiences rapidly, new media elevates the positive functions of democracy to a multifaceted and interactive level.

The negative functions of media on democracy become evident, particularly when high standards such as transparency, openness, social access, and democratic representation are not met. Media can create adverse effects by determining "what, how, and in what way society should know." The blurring of the line between news and commentary, along with the presence of hidden or implicit judgments in news selection and page layout, recalls Herman and Chomsky's "propaganda model" and the concept of "filters" (Dukul, 2022: 79). Such practices can lead to unexpected and erroneous outcomes in public opinion due to the media's provision of incorrect or incomplete information. Therefore, consumers must approach the presented content with a critical lens.

Pluralism is essential for the media to represent society and maintain a multi-voiced structure. However, a diverse and advanced media system alone does not guarantee service to democracy. It is critical for media owners and employees to act with a sense of collective responsibility to strengthen democracy. For the media to gain credibility, it must include the perspectives of all sides in controversial issues, provide explanatory information about claimed truths, and directly convey the statements of sources. Additionally, presenting concrete evidence whenever possible is also necessary (Işık, 2005: 119).

In modern societies, the negative effects of media on democracy are often linked to the dominance of power over the media. While mass communication tools are mechanisms for monitoring governance, government interventions in the media create a form of hegemony. According to Gramsci, the reproduction of power today is extended through consent rather than coercive methods; in this context, individual consciousness can become a field of conflict between political hegemony and opposing tendencies through the media (Gramsci, 2017: 68).

New media can also have both positive and negative effects on democracy. With the proliferation of digital platforms, content production has increased, and differently structured news sources have emerged. However, the abundance of both accurate and inaccurate

rate information has undermined the reliability of information and placed the responsibility of verification on the media.

Within the context of the global free-market economy, the media system has become an object of capitalism, and profit-oriented motives have become the primary factor determining content production. This process, which progresses in parallel with changes in media ownership, has brought the concept of the culture industry back into focus. According to Adorno, the media plays a significant role in legitimizing the culture industry; mass communication tools have been shaped to serve the culture industry, which has led to the manipulation of democracy by the media (Adorno, 2017: 318).

The Historical Development of Media in Turkey's Democratization Process

The late introduction of the printing press to the Ottoman Empire played a critical role in shaping Ottoman press history. Although Johannes Gutenberg invented the printing press in 1440, the first Turkish printing press in Ottoman lands was established by İbrahim Müteferrika in 1727, nearly three centuries later. The delay is attributed to factors such as the prevalence of calligraphy, concerns about unemployment among calligraphers, religious conservatism and bans, the unsuitability of Arabic script for printing, low literacy rates, and the lack of widespread reading habits (MEB, 2011: 4).

Tosun-Durmuş (2017: 966-967) suggests that this delay was linked not to backwardness but to the psychological effects of the Ottoman Empire's superiority over the West. Demir (2014: 59) points out that Ottoman bureaucrats became aware of the importance of the printing press only after the Greek uprisings.

During the reign of Sultan Ahmed III, a climate open to innovation allowed İbrahim Müteferrika to establish the printing press. With the approval of a religious decree from the Sheikh al-Islam, the printing press gained religious legitimacy, leading to the establishment of the first Muslim Turkish printing press in 1727 (MEB, 2011: 6). However, after Müteferrika's death, printing activities declined and continuity was only achieved during the Tanzimat Era.

During the Tanzimat Era, press activities intensified, particularly through newspapers. Sultan Mahmud II recognized the power of the press and published the first official newspaper, *Takvim-i Vekayi*, in 1831 (Öner, 2011: 152). Later, in 1840, the semi-official *Ceride-i Havadis* was published by William Churchill. However, these official newspapers lacked the capacity to critique the government or offer alternative viewpoints.

The need for an independent and critical press began to be met with the publication of *Tercüman-ı Ahval* in 1860 by Agah Efendi and Şinasi. Şinasi later published *Tasvir-i Efkar* in 1862. During this period, other newspapers like *Muhbir*, *Basiret*, and *İbret* also contributed to press diversity (Benek, 2016: 32-33).

The Young Ottomans movement, led by intellectuals such as Ziya Pasha, Namık Kemal, and Ali Suavi, emerged as an intellectual movement criticizing the government and advocating alternative governance

models (Koray, 1983: 563). Due to government pressures, these intellectuals moved abroad, continuing their activities in Paris and influencing public opinion through newspapers like *Hürriyet* (Duman, 2014: 41-42).

One of the key elements shaping the Ottoman press during the Tanzimat Era was press legislation. The *Printing Regulation* of 1857 required anyone wishing to open a printing house to obtain government permission (Ulusoy Nalcioğlu, 2005: 259). This regulation aimed to prevent anyone with capital from publishing books or newspapers. Articles 137 and 138 of the 1858 Penal Code prohibited the establishment of unauthorized printing houses and allowed for the seizure of publications against the state and the closure of offending printing houses (Duman, 2014: 34).

The rapid development of the press in the 1860s revealed the inadequacy of existing regulations, leading to the enactment of a new *Press Regulation* in 1864, modeled after the French Press Law. This regulation aimed to control media outlets and prevent publications against the state. However, the overseas activity of the Young Ottoman press necessitated stricter controls, resulting in the *Ali Decree* of 1867, which imposed harsher restrictions on the press (Topuz, 2018; Alan, 2019: 51). The first censorship practice began in 1876 but was soon lifted.

During this period, pressures on journalists increased, many newspapers were shut down, and journalists were forced into exile (Benek, 2016: 34). For instance, Namık Kemal's writings led to the repeated closure of *İbret*. These interventions deeply affected press activities and shaped subsequent press movements.

In the First Constitutional Era (1876-1878), press freedom briefly flourished. Although Article 12 of the constitution mentioned press freedom, older *Press Regulations* and decrees remained in effect (MEB, 2011: 14-15). With the onset of the Ottoman-Russian War, Sultan Abdul Hamid II dissolved parliament, ushering in the Era of Autocracy.

During the Era of Autocracy (1878-1908), strict censorship was imposed on the press. Sultan Abdul Hamid II tightly controlled the press, banning the use of words such as freedom, homeland, and republic (Koloğlu, 1992: 44). Despite this, newspapers like *Tercüman-ı Hakikat* by Ahmet Mithat Efendi, *Sabah* by Mihran Efendi, *İkdam*, *Tarik*, and *Mizan* were published. Journals gained greater importance during this period, with *Servet-i Fünun* leaving a significant impact on the literary and intellectual world (Koloğlu, 1992: 45-47).

Although Sultan Abdul Hamid's era is often seen as one of absolute authority, Çakır (2022: 434-435) argues that it should not be viewed as an anti-reform period. During this time, significant advancements occurred in transportation, healthcare, and education, as Sultan Abdul Hamid sought to manage the necessities of the modern world under his control. Rather than banning the press entirely, he subjected it to strict oversight, consolidating his power through newspapers under his control.

With the re-proclamation of the *Kanun-i Esasi* (Constitution) on July 23, 1908, the Second Constitutional Era began, and press restrictions were relaxed. For the first time, newspapers were published without censorship on July 25, 1908, leading to a rapid increase in newspapers and journals (Gülaçar, 2018: 112–113). However, this diversity also caused misinformation in the public sphere. Intellectuals of the era shared a common opposition to Sultan Abdul Hamid II. Following the Sultan's deposition on April 27, 1909, criticism of him became widespread in the press. However, after the *31 March Incident*, military censorship was reintroduced, limiting press freedom once again (Duman, 2014: 91–92).

The press during 1908–1914 was characterized by its lack of full guarantee of freedom. Periodical publications surged during this time, increasing from 120 to 750 within the first seven months of 1908 (Gülaçar, 2018: 114). The press became a tool for political groups and played a critical role in societal enlightenment (Gülaçar, 2018: 122–125). Ottoman intellectuals embraced ideologies like Ottomanism, Islamism, Westernism, and Turkism to prevent the empire's collapse, and these ideas found broad representation in the press. Meanwhile, nationalist sentiments grew among minority groups.

During this period, feminism advocating women's rights gained traction, and publications targeting women increased. Journals focusing on children, economics, and humor also proliferated. However, press freedom was not well understood or effectively implemented by either its practitioners or enforcers. Assassinations of journalists, such as Hasan Fehmi, Ahmet Samim, Zeki Bey, and Hasan Tahsin, highlighted the fragility of press freedom.

The press during the War of Independence can be categorized into three groups: those supporting the National Struggle, those opposing it, and foreign press outlets (Baykal, 1988: 471). Key figures in Istanbul's pro-National Struggle press included Yakup Kadri Karaosmanoğlu and Falih Rıfkı Atay of *İkdam*, Sedat Simavi of *Güleriüz*, Zekeriya and Sabiha Sertel of *Büyük Mecmua*, Hüseyin Cahit Yalçın of *Tanin*, and Velid Ebüzziya of *Tasvir-i Efkâr* (MEB, 2011: 25).

As noted by Güner (1998: 92), Istanbul's pro-National Struggle press could not openly resist due to heavy censorship by occupying forces. Newspapers such as *İleri*, *Yeni Gün*, *Akşam*, and *Vakit* supported the Anatolian movement. Conversely, newspapers like *Peyam-ı Sabah*, *Alemdar*, and *İstanbul* opposed the National Struggle, advocating for Ottoman territorial integrity under British protection.

Despite financial difficulties, distribution challenges, and shortages of paper, the Anatolian press operated effectively. Mustafa Kemal Atatürk, aware of the press's power in shaping public opinion, actively supported both the Anatolian press and sympathetic press in Istanbul, giving interviews and holding regular meetings with journalists (Baykal, 1988: 478). The publication of *Hâkimiyet-i Milliye* and Atatürk's authorship of its first editorial reflected the importance attributed to the press. Furthermore, Hasan Tahsin's symbolic resistance to the Greek occupation as editor-in-

chief of *Hukuk-u Beşer* highlighted the critical role of the Anatolian press in the struggle for independence.

Among the newspapers leading the National Struggle in Anatolia were *İrade-i Milliye*, *Hâkimiyet-i Milliye*, and *Öğüt*. Founded in 1920 by the decision of Mustafa Kemal Atatürk, the Anadolu Agency had two fundamental missions: introducing the Kuva-yi Milliye movement to the international public and keeping the public continuously informed.

Periodicals of the era included satirical magazines (*Diken*), women's magazines (*İnci*, *Yeni İnci*), children's magazines (*Çocuk Dünyası*), and literary magazines (*Ümit*). However, some publications, such as *Aydede* by Refik Halit Karay, adopted an anti-National Struggle stance (MEB, 2011: 30).

Following the victory of the War of Independence, the newly established Republic exiled journalists and writers who opposed the independence movement, including those on the "List of 150" such as Refik Halit Karay, Refii Cevat Ulunay, and Tarık Mümtaz Göktepe. After the proclamation of the Republic, the status of the caliphate became a contentious issue, leading to tensions between the Istanbul and Ankara press. Open letters opposing the abolition of the caliphate, letters of support for the caliph from India, and Hüseyin Cahit Yalçın's advocacy for keeping the caliphate in Turkey intensified these tensions (MEB, 2011: 36).

Despite Atatürk's calls for unity, some Istanbul newspapers continued their anti-Republican publications. Following the Sheikh Said Rebellion in 1925, the Grand National Assembly of Turkey enacted the Law on the Maintenance of Order (*Takrir-i Sükûn Kanunu*), leading to the closure of some newspapers. This law aimed to create a conducive environment for implementing reforms (Çelik, 1998: 151). Another significant development affecting the press during the early Republic was the transition to the Latin alphabet. Starting in 1928, some newspapers and magazines began using the new letters, while others adopted both old and new scripts. According to Tüfekçioğlu (1988: 89–90), the Alphabet Reform dealt a definitive blow to the traditional opposition press, and the government provided financial support to newspapers proportional to their contributions to the regime, effectively aligning the press with official ideology.

The *Press Law* adopted on July 25, 1931, aimed to prevent publications that could influence the country's general policies. This law brought the press largely under government control (Topuz, 1996: 89). Alongside legal regulations, the government imposed restrictions on the supply of paper, advertising, and printing materials. However, as Koloğlu (1992: 62) points out, censorship was notably absent in the local press during Atatürk's era. During this period, the press was encouraged to align its publications with the *Misak-ı Milli* (National Pact) understanding, and in 1933, the Press Directorate was established.

The *Press Congress* held in 1935, with the participation of government and Republican People's Party (CHP) leaders, addressed the issues of the press. Representatives from private newspapers and magazines were invited, and the establishment of a press union was decided (Duman, 2014: 145). In 1938, the Press

Law was revised, introducing requirements such as a guarantee letter for those wishing to publish newspapers and magazines and banning individuals with a "bad reputation" from working in the press (Topuz, 1996: 95). Prominent newspapers during this period included *Cumhuriyet*, *Akşam*, *Tan*, *Ulus*, and *Vakit*. The 1930s also saw a rise in intellectual periodicals, including *Kadro*, *Varlık*, *Yeni Adam*, and *Yedigün* (Koloğlu, 1992: 66).

During World War II, Turkey experienced a tense environment, with the CHP prioritizing control to keep the country out of the war. This situation hindered democratic initiatives and the development of the press (Duman, 2014: 146). Divisions emerged in the press, with some newspapers advocating democracy while others supported closer ties with Germany. Martial law declared in 1940 further restricted press freedom, leading to the closure of many newspapers and magazines (MEB, 2011: 43–44).

The socio-economic effects of the war negatively impacted the press industry. Paper shortages forced newspapers to reduce their page counts and publication frequency, making it difficult for new publications to emerge. During this period, global trends toward multiparty systems resonated in Turkey, eventually paving the way for Turkey's transition to a multiparty democracy.

As Turkey transitioned to a multiparty system in 1946, the CHP government repealed Article 50 of the *Press Law*, which had been a significant obstacle to press freedom. This development fostered a hopeful atmosphere for press freedom during the election preparations. According to Orhan Koloğlu, the global pressure for pluralism and freedom mirrored the press boom seen in 1908 (Koloğlu, 1992: 68).

During the 1940s, the press became a primary means of communication across the country, with hundreds of newspapers and magazines being published. Radio, which had been influential during wartime, lost its impact. In 1941, while the total circulation of newspapers in Turkey was only 60,000, with no single paper exceeding 20,000 copies and 227 magazines being published, by 1946, these numbers surged to 202 newspapers and 302 magazines, with daily circulation nearing 100,000 (Koloğlu, 1992: 70–71). According to Gürkan (1998), prominent daily newspapers included *Vatan*, *Cumhuriyet*, *Tanin*, *Vakit*, *Yeni Sabah*, *Tasvir*, *Akşam*, *Posta*, and *Son Telgraf*. Additionally, newspapers such as *Hürriyet*, *Yeni Asır*, and *Tan*—despite facing severe attacks and closures in 1945—were significant publications of this period (cited in Yeşilçayır, 2011: 135).

One notable development of the 1950s was the establishment of *Türkiye Haber Ajansı* by Kadri Kayabal, marking the first private news agency of the Republic era (Topuz, 1996: 182).

The 1950 general elections were a turning point for press freedom in Turkey. The Democrat Party (DP) came to power with a liberal discourse and enacted the 1950 *Press Law*. This law abolished the requirement for government approval and licensing for publishing newspapers and magazines, lifted previous restrictions, and eliminated the adjudication of press offenses in special courts, granting significant freedoms to the

press (Laçiner, 2015: 194). Additionally, the 5953 Law passed on June 13, 1952, granted journalists rights such as unionization, social security, job security, and paid leave (MEB, 2011: 52–53).

However, the DP's favorable stance towards the press began to change after the 1954 general elections. The 1954 *Law No. 6334* curtailed press freedom, stripping journalists of their right to substantiate their reports, sparking international criticism (Laçiner, 2015: 196–197). Following the 6–7 September 1955 events, the DP government took harsher measures against the press, implementing martial law and closing newspapers. Publications like *Ulus* and *Kültür* were shut down indefinitely, while others like *Hürriyet*, *Tercüman*, *Her Gün*, *Kültür*, and *Dünya* faced 15-day suspensions (MEB, 2011: 54).

In 1956, laws further limiting press freedom were enacted, criminalizing "malicious or personal publications" and banning coverage of confidential government or party meetings. The government also used economic pressure to control the press, placing state monopolies on official advertising and announcements in 1957, creating financial challenges for newspapers (MEB, 2011: 54). During this time, a media structure favoring the government—referred to as the "partisan press"—emerged (Laçiner, 2015: 197).

Between 1954 and 1960, 1,161 journalists were prosecuted, with 238 convictions. Newspapers like *Yeni Sabah* and *Milliyet* were shut down, and the arrests of journalists gained widespread media coverage (MEB, 2011: 55). Amid escalating tensions with the opposition Republican People's Party (CHP), the DP established an Investigation Committee on April 27, 1960, which blocked the printing and distribution of non-compliant publications. This period ended on May 27, 1960, when the Armed Forces, under the National Unity Committee (MBK), seized power, marking the beginning of a new era (MEB, 2011: 55–56).

The MBK, before transferring power to the Constituent Assembly, enacted two significant laws. The *Law No. 212* (Press Workers' Law) and the *Law No. 195* granted journalists key rights, including severance pay, compensation in cases of death or closure, job security, paid leave for night workers, and the right to have disputes heard in labor courts rather than commercial courts. The Press Workers' Day on January 10 commemorates the implementation of these rights. Another major reform was the establishment of the Press Advertising Agency (*Basın İlan Kurumu*) under *Law No. 195*, aimed at regulating official advertising and eliminating biased press practices (Topuz, 1996: 122–123).

The 1961 Constitution included significant provisions related to the press, stating: "The press is free and cannot be censored; publication bans cannot be imposed; newspapers and magazines cannot be confiscated or closed; prior authorization is not required for publishing newspapers or magazines; dissemination of news, ideas, and opinions cannot be obstructed; and printing presses cannot be confiscated." It also guaranteed the right to reply and correction and obligated the state to provide means for exercising communication

rights (Laçiner, 2015: 199-200). These measures ensured press freedom while incorporating safeguards to prevent abuse.

Despite the revival of press activity during this period, restrictions soon resurfaced. The 1962 Precautionary Law was one of the first to limit press freedom after the 1961 Constitution. The situation worsened following the March 12, 1971, memorandum, which led to the resignation of Süleyman Demirel's government and the declaration of martial law in 11 provinces. Operations during this period saw numerous prominent journalists arrested. These pressures culminated in amendments to Articles 22 and 27 of the 1961 Constitution, transferring the authority to confiscate newspapers and magazines from judges to prosecutors (Laçiner, 2015: 201).

During this period, many journalists were arrested. For example, Turhan Dilligil, Doğan Koloğlu, Alpay Kabacalı, and Sabri Yıldız were prosecuted for their previous writings, while Çetin Altan was sentenced to prison for a speech he made while serving as a member of parliament. Additionally, İlhan Selçuk and editor-in-chief Oktay Kurtböke were arrested on April 27, 1971, due to Selçuk's article titled "*Welcome, Tanzimat Mentality*" (*Hoş Geldin Tanzimat Kafası*), and *Cumhuriyet* newspaper was shut down for 10 days. However, the case ultimately ended in acquittal (MEB, 2011: 60).

The 1973 general elections marked the beginning of a normalization in Turkey's political climate, as a general amnesty was enacted during this period.

Development Dynamics and Perspectives of Contemporary Turkish Media in the Context of Democracy

The global transformations of the 1980s led to profound changes in the media sector. One of the primary dynamics of this transformation was the focus of economic policies on the information industry as a response to addressing stagnation and inflation. The adoption of right-wing policies in Western societies brought significant changes to political, economic, and social structures. The economic strategies embraced in the U.S. and the U.K. eventually influenced Europe and other countries. To combat rising stagflation, there was an increasing tendency toward industry policies based on information technologies.

This restructuring process triggered a visual and auditory revolution in the information industry and the media sector. During the 1980s, major broadcasting groups experienced regional and global growth, laying the groundwork for global communication. The media sector transitioned from public monopolies to private broadcasting enterprises, fostering the development of diverse organizational structures and profit-driven mechanisms. The shift to a free-market economy during this period led to monopolistic tendencies dominating media ownership, economic conditions, and institutional infrastructures.

By the 1990s, the concept of "media" encompassing newspapers, magazines, cinema, radio, and television became widespread. This term, adopted by the advertising industry, referred to all platforms where advertisements could be published. For Turkey, 1990 marked a turning point, with the establishment of the first private radio and television channels, leading to

the launch of hundreds of TV channels and thousands of radio stations (Pekman, 2014: 221). The commercialization of media influenced content production and the form of media tools, resulting in more colorful and multi-page newspapers and the proliferation of entertainment programs on television. The integration of the internet into this process elevated media transformation to its peak.

Internet-based new media brought about radical changes in global communication technologies. This transition, referred to as digital media, introduced significant innovations in the recording, storage, and distribution of information. The traditional analog media was reprocessed and expanded, leading to significant transformations in media production, distribution, and consumption. New concepts such as "digitality," "hypertextuality," "virtuality," "network-based," and "simulation" entered the literature (Lister et al., 2009: 125).

During this period, societal structures were redefined in various ways. While McLuhan described this new structure as a "global village," Castells introduced the concept of the "network society." These developments were reflected in Turkish media, which became more interactive, dynamic, and multidimensional.

The military coup of September 12, 1980, led to profound changes in Turkey's political, societal, and media landscape. Declarations following the coup dissolved parliament and the government, imposed martial law nationwide, and lifted the immunity of parliamentarians. The economic measures known as the *January 24 Decisions* marked the beginning of fundamental changes in both political/social life and the press. The 1980 coup is considered a turning point in the relationship between media and political power in Turkey (Utma, 2010: 139). After the end of military rule, Turgut Özal became prime minister following the 1983 elections.

In terms of press history, one of the most notable aspects of the post-1980 structural transformation was the development of magazine publishing. The military intervention's restrictions on political publications for several years created a void, which was filled by high-quality magazines. Publications such as *Haftasonu*, *TV 7 Gün*, *Haftanın Sesi*, *Merhaba*, *Hayat*, *Hey*, and *Ses* emerged during this period, while satirical magazines like *Gırgır*, *Fırt*, and *Çarşaf* gained popularity. Children's magazines included *Milliyet Çocuk*, *Tercüman Çocuk*, *Türkiye Çocuk*, and *Hürriyet Çocuk*, while *Yankı* stood out in the political magazine category. Additionally, *Bilim Teknik* garnered attention for its scientific content, while monthly magazines such as *Ev Kadını*, *Erkekçe*, *Bravo*, *Onyedi*, *Kadınca*, and *Kadın* entered the publishing world (MEB, 2011: 63).

The 1980s were shaped by economic liberalization policies and the increasing prevalence of terrorism in eastern and southeastern Turkey. During this period, the press faced significant challenges, including lawsuits against many newspapers, imprisonment of journalists, and bans on publications. Particularly after 1984, state security was treated as a more sensitive issue, and the State Security Courts began implementing preventive measures against publications perceived as threats to national security.

The 1990s marked a period of major transformations in television broadcasting in Turkey. The monopoly of TRT (Turkish Radio and Television Corporation) ended with the emergence of private channels. The first private television channel, *Star 1*, was established in 1990 by the Uzan family. Subsequently, channels like *Show TV*, *HBB*, *Kanal 6*, *TGRT*, *Kanal D*, *ATV*, and *STV* began broadcasting (Laçiner, 2015: 205–207).

The commercialization of media significantly altered the nature of news bulletins. Unlike TRT's formal and protocol-driven broadcasts, private channels reduced international news coverage and prioritized entertainment-oriented content (Akkor Gül, 2011: 28). The media ownership concentration that began in the 1980s accelerated in the 1990s, increasing the influence of media owners over political and economic power.

Due to rising terrorism, the Anti-Terror Law was enacted in 1991, prohibiting press activities that threatened the unity and integrity of the state. In the same year, 73 lawsuits were filed against newspapers and journalists, 77 newspapers and magazines were confiscated, and 19 journalists were killed—these murders remain a dark stain in the history of Turkish journalism.

After 1994, the media sector took steps toward stabilization and normalization. Major media groups and conglomerates entered the industry, ending periods of high costs and destructive competition. For example, *Show TV*, *ATV*, and *Kanal D* established joint advertising sales companies to reduce competition within the sector (Aksoy and Robins, 1997: 1951).

At the beginning of the 2000s, Turkey faced significant economic problems, including a growing public deficit, high debt, interest rates, and inflation, culminating in a deep economic crisis in 2001 (Şahin, 2010: 37). These crises profoundly affected the media sector, which transformed into a structure operating primarily in the interests of its owners. Cross-media ownership and monopolization became central topics of debate. Cross-media ownership refers to media institutions operating across multiple fields under the same group's control. Companies pursued this strategy to expand their reach and increase readership (Kuyucu, 2013: 150).

During this time, the journalist-employer tradition, which had begun with the *Cumhuriyet* newspaper, ended. Media outlets fell into the hands of non-journalistic owners or merged with non-journalistic activities, marking the end of the artisanal era in journalism. The mission of informing the public gave way to profit-driven goals aligned with market demand. This transformation affected the sector's conceptual framework, with the term "media" replacing "press," and monopolistic tendencies intensified as relations with political power deepened. The economic growth of the media sector relied heavily on treasury resources provided through state banks, linked to rapid increases in production costs.

Monopolization in the Turkish media sector reached a point where companies needed substantial capital and at least a 40% market share to enter the industry. The market was dominated by five or six major

companies, resulting in homogeneous products of similar quality. This process accelerated cartelization, with anti-competitive agreements increasing in distribution and advertising (Dikenova-Yıldız, 2010: 66).

By the early 2000s, the *Doğan* and *Bilgin* groups held significant dominance in the media, consolidating their distribution powers to form a monopoly. Following the *Etibank* scandal, the Bilgin Group lost influence, and the joint distribution company *Yaysat* came under the control of the Doğan Group. In October 2002, the Bilgin Group formed United Press with the *Çukurova* and *Cumhuriyet* newspapers. In November 2002, the *Yeni Şafak* newspaper, known for its proximity to the Justice and Development Party (AKP), joined this publishing group. Organizations like the Turkish Journalists Association, the Ankara Journalists Association, and the Contemporary Journalists Association welcomed efforts to break media monopolies (Dikenova-Yıldız, 2010: 67).

During this period, the Turkish media sector came under the dominance of large capital groups that operated in banking, construction, energy, and textiles, among other industries. Prominent groups included the *Doğan Group*, *Doğuş Group*, *Çukurova Group*, *Ciner Group*, *Çalık Group*, *İhlas Group*, and *Feza Journalism* (Şahin, 2010: 19-29).

The Justice and Development Party (AKP), which came to power in 2002, pursued policies to consolidate its influence in the media through regulatory strategies and an oligarchic media structure (Başaran-İnce, 2020: 23). In its first term (2002–2008), the government adopted dialogue- and consensus-oriented policies to gain both domestic and international support (Ayan, 2019: 48). Although a positive atmosphere for pluralism and criticism was fostered, media ownership was restructured. Using the Savings Deposit Insurance Fund (TMSF), certain media outlets were seized and transferred to groups aligned with the AKP. Additionally, new media outlets were established with the support of Islamic capital, and mainstream media came under the influence of government-aligned journalists and intellectuals (Ayan, 2019: 56).

From 2008 to 2013, the government's dominance over the media became increasingly evident, marking a period of transformation in media policies. Strategies such as restructuring through the establishment of media outlets based on Islamic bourgeoisie, the acquisition of existing institutions, and the rise of pro-AKP journalists in central media were employed (Ayan, 2019: 141).

Between 2013 and 2018, Turkey faced major crises, including the *Gezi Park Protests* and the *July 15, 2016 coup attempt*. During this time, the government intensified its control over the media through pressure-oriented and power-focused policies (Ayan, 2019: 162). Following the coup attempt, many media outlets were shut down, journalists were imprisoned, and press freedom was severely curtailed (Alrmizan, 2019: 33). Akser and Baybars (2022: 1) highlight that Turkish media during this period was trapped in a competitive authoritarian media regime, with both pro-government and opposition media elements under pressure.

After 2018, similar strategies persisted, with the media continuing to serve as a tool for consolidating governmental power. The government increasingly influenced media ownership and content production through strategies of acquisition, capture, restructuring, and suppression. This period saw strengthened mechanisms of control over media ownership and production, directing media organizations to align their content with government policies.

The transformation of Turkish media during the Justice and Development Party (AKP) era was influenced by structural factors such as the proliferation of the internet, independent of government policies. However, the dominance of private broadcasting in terms of newspaper content and ownership structures became increasingly apparent. Economic crises and financial challenges led some major media groups to exit the industry, transferring media outlets to relatively new market players. The Savings Deposit Insurance Fund (TMSF) played a critical role during this process, with media ownership often shifting based on proximity to the AKP.

The period from 2002 to 2008 marked the transformation of media ownership and control dynamics in favor of the AKP, leading to the emergence of what has been called the "AKP media." This process fostered an atmosphere of silence and compliance in the media sector. As Ayan (2019: 65-66) notes, when the AKP came to power, it already had the support of media outlets like *Zaman*, *Yeni Şafak*, *Yeni Akit*, *Kanal 7*, and *Samanyolu TV*. The AKP further strengthened its media base by establishing new outlets such as *ATV-Sabah*, *TVNET*, *Ülke TV*, *24 TV*, and *Taraf*, supported by TMSF and Islamic capital. These developments were driven by the rise of conservative capital and the use of state resources to benefit this segment. Through public tenders, privatizations, and tax regulations, the AKP built its own capital class, which expanded investments into sectors like energy, construction, security, and healthcare (Çarık, 2022: 260-261).

Civil society became a significant mechanism in media ownership. Institutions such as primary and secondary schools, universities, think tanks, foundations, charitable associations, professional unions, and the Directorate of Religious Affairs played a role in shaping media authority in Turkey (Ayan, 2019: 129). In this environment, the media largely lost its independent voice, and professional groups in journalism and media faced difficulties in securing proper working conditions. Consequently, existing media owners became key actors shaping both daily life and the political agenda.

The AKP's media policy evolved through stages, focusing on power politics as a means of building consent and establishing hegemony (Ayan, 2019: 81). One of the most striking examples of these policies was the state of emergency declared in 2016. During this period, numerous universities, associations, private healthcare and education institutions, foundations, and media outlets were closed without any investigations (Ayan, 2019: 184).

Self-censorship became widespread in the media during the AKP era. With increasing state influence

over the media, the Radio and Television Supreme Council (RTÜK) was often criticized for losing its impartiality and acting as a censorship tool for the government. Allegations include prioritizing political loyalty over merit in staffing, offering high salaries to politically aligned individuals, and allowing unproductive employees to benefit from high incomes and privileges. These practices are viewed as indicative of clientelistic networks shaping the council's personnel policies and outcomes (Laçiner, 2015: 403).

While various efforts continue in Turkey to protect and promote human rights, significant challenges in this area have also emerged. In this context, the relationship between human rights and media becomes a critical subject, with the state of freedom of expression being a central topic in all media systems. Freedom of expression, as part of a democratic understanding, is recognized as essential for accessing information, disclosing matters of public concern, and enabling discussion (Marcusson, 2011: 1). In Turkey, significant and comprehensive regulations on freedom of expression and press freedom have been introduced within the framework of judicial reforms, particularly those initiated during the EU harmonization process and continuing in the fields of law and criminal justice. However, persistent issues related to freedom of expression and press freedom remain.

Addressing and resolving issues of freedom of expression and press freedom require fundamental changes in governance, the judicial system, and societal attitudes. Moreover, the full establishment of freedom of expression necessitates the development of public awareness and a culture of democracy. A societal approach that embraces the defense of fundamental rights and freedoms can ensure that freedom of expression is firmly grounded (Yıldırım, 2012: 83–84).

An important element in the context of freedom of expression is internet-based new media. The transition from traditional to new media has led to profound changes not only in the form but also in the content of media. Communication methods have also shifted. Unlike traditional media with limited interaction opportunities, new media offers individuals a higher level of direct interaction and active participation (Hong and Liang, 2015: 251).

New media broadly encompasses all political and/or social activities facilitated by internet technologies, including both digital and offline activities. In this regard, citizen journalism forms an important part of new media and is noteworthy in the context of freedom of expression (Democratic Progress Institute, 2012: 13).

New media plays a vital role in enhancing political participation. The internet facilitates forms of political gatherings, enabling individuals to come together. The emergence of social media has expanded the ways in which politics can be influenced. In this context, new media serves as a platform for producing political information, fostering political participation, and strengthening forms of engagement (Calderaro, 2018: 793).

The functionality of new media in the context of freedom of expression in Turkey became evident during events such as the *Gezi Park Protests*. Through social media platforms, citizens were able to share their opinions, criticisms, and perspectives on various political, social, cultural, and economic issues. The Gezi protests stand out as an example of individuals sharing their views via social media, connecting with like-minded groups, and forming a collective movement. This illustrates that new media offers a new domain for freedom of expression.

Conclusion

This study aims to analyze the role of media in Turkey's democratization process from a historical perspective, examining the contributions of media to democracy and the challenges encountered in this journey. Spanning from the Ottoman Empire to the construction of the modern Republic and the current media landscape, the interaction between media and democracy has undergone continuous transformation. Historically, the media has served as both a tool supporting democratization and a field constrained by oppressive policies.

The late introduction of the printing press during the Ottoman period and the state-controlled nature of early press activities limited the development of the media-democracy relationship in its initial stages. While the Tanzimat and Constitutional periods achieved some progress in press freedom and pluralism, the control mechanisms over the media during these eras fell short of fully supporting democratization. With the establishment of the Republic, modernization and reform processes enhanced the role of media in fostering social awareness. However, political pressures on the media persisted, particularly during the single-party regime and subsequent military interventions.

Starting in the 1980s, the impact of neoliberal policies brought fundamental changes to media ownership structures and operations. The rise of private radio and television channels was a positive step toward media pluralism, but this process also led to trends of monopolization and the influence of commercial concerns on media content. During the Justice and Development Party (AKP) era, media became a more pronounced tool for shaping political policies. Transformations in media control and ownership during this period have raised concerns about pluralism and freedom.

For the media to effectively serve democracy, it must be capable of upholding freedom of expression, pluralism, and balance and oversight mechanisms. However, in Turkey, the media has historically struggled to fully fulfill these ideal functions due to the influence of various political regimes and economic dynamics. Nevertheless, the development of new media technologies and social media presents new opportunities for freedom of expression and civic engagement. Social media, in particular, has demonstrated its potential to enhance individual participation in democratization processes and amplify diverse voices to reach broader audiences.

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